

Supplemental Material

Research Articles | Cellular/Molecular

Distinct regulation of early trafficking of the NMDA receptors by the ligand-binding domains of the GluN1 and GluN2A subunits

<https://doi.org/10.1523/JNEUROSCI.0226-24.2025>

Received: 2 February 2024

Revised: 13 March 2025

Accepted: 8 May 2025

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Supplementary Material Legends

Figure S1 Representative images of HEK293 cells transfected with the ARIAD-mNEON-GluN2A construct alone or with the WT GluN1-4a subunit at 0 min (without AL) and 60 min after adding AL. The total and surface levels (top and bottom row, respectively) of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN2A subunits were labeled using an anti-mNEONGreen antibody 24 hours after the transfection.

Figure S2 (A, B) Summary of relative surface expression of NMDARs containing WT ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a construct together with GluN2A (**A**) or GluN3A (**B**) subunits in the presence (120, 60, 30 min) or absence (0 min) of AL. *** $p < 0.001$ vs 0 min of AL; one-way ANOVA. Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 39$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM.

Figure S3 Summary of the average intensity of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunit signal co-localized in the presence of AL in indicated times with GM130 over the average intensity of ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a subunit signal outside the GM130 signal, calculated for the indicated NMDAR combinations. *** $p < 0.001$ for differences between ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN3A receptor in the absence and presence of AL; Student's t -test. For ARIAD-mNEON-GluN1-1a/GluN2A receptor at different time points in the presence of AL, no significant differences were found using one-way ANOVA ($p > 0.05$). Data points correspond to individual cells ($n \geq 20$), and the red box plot represents mean \pm SEM.

Figure S4 (A) Representative images of HEK293 cells expressing the WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A or GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-S511A receptors. Surface GFP epitopes were labeled with Alexa Fluor 647 (top), and internalized GFP epitopes were labeled with Alexa Fluor 555 (middle); merged surface and internalized GFP-labeled signals are shown in the bottom. **(B)** Summary of the relative surface expression (left side) and the ratio of internalized versus surface (right side) of the WT GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A or GluN1-4a/GFP-GluN2A-S511A receptors; ($n \geq 145$), *** $p < 0.001$ vs. WT; Student's t -test.

Figure S5 Normalized concentration-response curves for L-glutamate effect at NMDARs containing the indicated mutation obtained by fitting the data using *Equation (1)* (see Methods); for a summary of fitting parameters, see Table 3.

Figure S6 Representative whole-cell patch-clamp recordings of HEK293 cells transfected with the indicated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors. Glycine (gly) at the indicated concentrations was applied in the continuous presence of 100 μ M L-glutamate (L-glu). The following glycine concentrations were used for the measurements: YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A (4.5; 3.0 μ M), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688A/hGluN2A (7.5;

5.0 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688Y/hGluN2A (4,200; 2,800 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A (4,720 μM); for higher concentrations, τ_{on} values <40 ms), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688C/hGluN2A (41; 27 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688N/hGluN2A (225; 150 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688W/hGluN2A (3,375; 2,250 μM).

Figure S7 Correlation analysis of K_d and EC_{50} values for glycine for WT and mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing the mutant cycle of the GluN1-S688 residue; fitted by linear regression. For a description of the calculation of K_d , see Text S1; for fitting parameters, see Table S1.

Figure S8 Representative whole-cell patch-clamp recordings from HEK293 cells transfected with the indicated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors. L-glutamate (L-glu) at the indicated concentrations was applied in the presence of 100 μM glycine (gly). The following concentrations of L-glutamate were used for the measurements: YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A (7.5; 5.0 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511A (270; 180 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511P (105; 70 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511C (390; 260 μM), YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A-S511E (510; 340 μM).

Figure S9 Correlation analysis of K_d and EC_{50} values for L-glutamate for WT and mutated YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A receptors containing the mutant cycle of the GluN2A-S511 residue; fitted by linear regression. For a description of the calculation of K_d , see Text S1; for fitting parameters, see Table S1.

Figure S10 Representative RMSF fluctuations of $\text{C}\alpha$ residues in the LBD of the GluN1 subunit for the indicated mutations. The residue numbering follows the full-length GluN1 subunit. The black arrow indicates residue position 688 in the full-length GluN1 subunit.

Figure S11 Representative RMSF fluctuations of fluctuation $\text{C}\alpha$ residues in the LBD of the GluN2A subunit for the indicated mutations. The residue numbering follows the full-length GluN2A subunit. The black arrow indicates residue position 511 in the full-length GluN2A subunit.

Table S1. Summary of the fitting parameters for calculating K_d values for glycine or L-glutamate measured from the HEK293 cells expressing human versions of GluN1/GluN2A receptors carrying the indicated mutant cycle substitutions

Figure S1

-AL
GluN1-4a/
ARIAD-
mNEON-GluN2A

+AL 60 min
GluN1-4a/
ARIAD-
mNEON-GluN2A

Total

Surface

Figure S2

A

B

Figure S3

Figure S4

Figure S5

Figure S6

YFP-hGluN1-1a/hGluN2A

YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688Y/hGluN2A

Figure S7

Figure S8

Figure S9

1 **Table S1.** Summary of the fitting parameters for calculating K_d values for glycine or L-glutamate measured
 2 from the HEK293 cells expressing human versions of GluN1/GluN2A receptors carrying the indicated mutant
 3 cycle substitutions.

Receptor	Agonist	τ_{off} (s)	k_{off} (s^{-1})	k_{on} ($\mu M^{-1}s^{-1}$)	K_d (μM)	n
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.243 \pm 0.017	4.171 \pm 0.262	1.870 \pm 0.164	2.424 \pm 0.243	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688A/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.242 \pm 0.018	4.239 \pm 0.310	1.215 \pm 0.127	3.646 \pm 0.531	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688Y/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.128 \pm 0.006	8.035 \pm 0.403	0.003 \pm 0.000	2,734.821 \pm 181.083	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688P/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.117 \pm 0.015	9.250 \pm 1.481	0.001 \pm 0.000	8,111.366 \pm 473.845	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688C/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.163 \pm 0.008	6.215 \pm 0.316	0.257 \pm 0.012	26.674 \pm 1.690	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688N/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.166 \pm 0.020	6.539 \pm 0.913	0.049 \pm 0.003	143.729 \pm 14.698	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a- S688W/ hGluN2A	glycine	0.129 \pm 0.009	7.202 \pm 0.447	0.003 \pm 0.000	2,244.545 \pm 94.634	6
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A	L- glutamate	0.156 \pm 0.002	6.466 \pm 0.079	1.416 \pm 0.101	4.684 \pm 0.358	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511A	L- glutamate	0.166 \pm 0.018	6.317 \pm 0.650	0.050 \pm 0.003	132.748 \pm 15.605	5
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511P	L- glutamate	0.151 \pm 0.011	6.912 \pm 0.467	0.112 \pm 0.009	63.020 \pm 4.223	7
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511C	L- glutamate	0.188 \pm 0.029	5.906 \pm 0.935	0.028 \pm 0.003	211.768 \pm 14.050	4
YFP-hGluN1-1a/ hGluN2A-S511E	L- glutamate	0.150 \pm 0.011	6.925 \pm 0.528	0.024 \pm 0.002	302.416 \pm 32.213	4

4 All parameters were calculated as described in Text S1. The concentrations of glycine or L-glutamate
 5 used for the measurements are described in Figure S6 and S8 legends.

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 9

1 **Text S1**

2 *Estimation of K_d values*

3 To determine the dissociation constant (K_d), we analyzed the onset and offset kinetics of ligand binding
4 by fitting the onset and offset of the current responses of the WT and mutant GluN1/GluN2A receptors.
5 For most GluN1/GluN2A receptors, we used their rounded values of EC_{50} and $1.5 \times EC_{50}$ for glycine or
6 L-glutamate in the continuous presence of $100 \mu\text{M}$ L-glutamate or glycine, respectively; we did not
7 employ $>10,000 \mu\text{M}$ glycine or L-glutamate due to concern about the effect of high osmolarity on our
8 measurements (Figure S6 and S8). The onset (τ_{on}) and offset (τ_{off}) time constant values were obtained by
9 fitting the experimental data using a single-exponential equation. The onset rate constant (k_{on}) was
10 determined according to *Equation (2)*: $k_{on} = ((1/\tau_{on}) - k_{off})/[\text{agonist concentration}]$. The offset rate
11 constant (k_{off}) value was determined as the average of the $1/\tau_{off}$ values measured for tested glycine or L-
12 glutamate concentrations (Horak et al., 2004). The K_d value was determined using *Equation (3)*: $K_d =$
13 k_{off}/k_{on} . Estimating K_d values using τ_{on} and τ_{off} values is not entirely precise, as it does not account for
14 agonist efficacy. In addition, the ~ 20 ms solution exchange time might limit the measured time
15 constants. Therefore, we used τ_{on} and τ_{off} values obtained with EC_{50} and $1.5 \times EC_{50}$ concentrations for
16 glycine or L-glutamate, as they reached >40 ms; the YFP-hGluN1-1a-S688P/hGluN2A receptor
17 exhibited τ_{on} value >40 ms at $4,720 \mu\text{M}$ glycine concentration ($0.5 \times EC_{50}$); the YFP-hGluN1-1a-
18 S688E/hGluN2A receptor exhibited $\tau_{on} > \tau_{off}$ (measured at $3,040$ and $4,560 \mu\text{M}$ glycine concentrations),
19 which precluded the estimation of K_d value by the described approach (see also Figure S6).

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